

ENHANCING STUDENTS' CRITICAL THINKING THROUGH READING: IN THE SAMPLE OF «PASSANGER TO FRANKFURT»

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Abstract. *This article examines the central role of reading in foreign language teaching, emphasizing its multifaceted importance for the development of linguistic, analytical and cultural skills of students. The author uses Agatha Christie's book «Passenger to Frankfurt» as a concrete example of the successful application of fiction in the educational process and describes how the selected book contributes to an exciting learning process, allowing students not only to learn the language but also to explore cultural nuances. The article also provides practical advice for teachers. The conclusion sums up what has been said, emphasizing that reading fiction can serve not only as a tool for language learning, but also as a bridge to cultural awareness and analytical thinking.*

Keywords: *Critical thinking, language literacy, students' perception, communicative skills.*

Аннотация. *Эта статья рассматривает центральную роль чтения в преподавании иностранных языков, подчеркивая его многогранное значение для развития лингвистических, аналитических и культурных навыков студентов. Автор использует книгу Агаты Кристи «Пассажир во Франкфурте» как конкретный пример успешного применения художественной литературы в образовательном процессе и описывает, как выбранная книга способствует захватывающему процессу обучения, позволяя студентам не только изучать язык, но и исследовать культурные нюансы. Статья также содержит практические рекомендации для учителей. Заключение резюмирует сказанное, подчеркивая, что чтение литературы может служить не только инструментом для изучения языка, но и мостом к культурному сознанию и аналитическому мышлению.*

Ключевые слова. *Критическое мышление, языковая грамотность, восприятие учащихся, коммуникативные навыки.*

In the world of foreign language learning, reading plays a key role in developing all language skills. It helps not only to expand the vocabulary but also to strengthen grammatical knowledge, improve listening perception, and develop the ability to use the language independently. However, many students often perceive reading as one of the most difficult and boring parts of learning. But what if reading can be turned into an exciting process that helps not

only in language practice but also in cultural and intellectual development? A striking example of this approach is the use of fiction, as it was in my class with students of the faculty of International Relations, where we discussed Agatha Christie’s book "Passenger to Frankfurt". While working with the text, students not only improved their language skills but also developed important analytical skills.

Reading is the basis for several aspects of learning a certain language, and this is quite obvious. Every time a student opens a book in a foreign language, he or she is introduced to a new vocabulary, which facilitates the acquisition of new words. He observes the use of phrases and words in context, which allows him to understand their meaning and master their use. It is important to emphasize that reading is not just an act of perception, it also helps to develop other skills.

Reading also plays a significant role in improving grammar skills. When reading various texts, students intuitively learn the grammatical structures, which allows them to apply them in oral speech. In contrast to standard grammar exercises, reading contributes to a deeper understanding of the functioning of language in real contexts, creating a solid foundation for free communication.

Reading also significantly improves listening skills. Active reading helps students develop the ability to perceive language just by listening, as they become more familiar with different language structures, pronunciation and intonation. This, in turn, facilitates the understanding of speech, which is an important aspect of learning any foreign language.

Finally, reading promotes critical thinking and analytical skills. Kurland (2000) remarks critical thinking and critical reading work together in harmony. He indicated that critical thinking will allow readers to monitor their understanding as they read. By analyzing text, whether it is an artwork or informational material, students learn to identify hidden meanings, understand context, draw conclusions, and build logical connections. This is an important aspect that can be useful not only in learning but also in other spheres of life.

"Passenger to Frankfurt" as an example

Reading motivation is an important factor which supports students to read more, and it has a significant relationship with reading and understanding texts (M.R. Ahmadi 2012). Wang (2008) pointed out that students who study a foreign language need to improve their reading ability in order to comprehend the texts (Rosenfeld, Leung, & Oltman, 2001). It is concluded that, additional benefits of being a motivated reader by stating that it is important to motivate students to read by providing them opportunities to select their desired materials. In other words, readers need to read more when they are allowed to choose their reading materials because they would discover that reading is an enjoyable activity (Pachtman & Wilson, 2006), also is exciting and stimulating their interest in reading. In this regard, *"Passenger to Frankfurt"* by Agatha Christie was a great choice. A book written by a master of the detective genre provides an exciting storyline that simultaneously develops attention to detail, critical thinking, and language literacy. As I have made a survey about the book, the followings are the responses of the students about the choice of the book:

- *“I realized that this book was for me, because I am a huge fan of detective books. I can say that this book is not only about crime, it is about politics as well. For me, it was so helpful to understand the world. The book is very useful for people who are interested in politics; it provides the information about the life of diplomats and about the relations between countries. I recommend it to everyone. “*

- *“Honestly, I have never read a book in any foreign language and this book is the first that I have ever read. After reading this book I began to be interested in reading English books like this novel. “The “Passenger to Frankfurt” is related to our profession and I have gained a lot of impressions from it. I learnt how a diplomat should be and how to solve social and political issues. I saw the entire life of an ambassador and drew my own conclusions. It is engaging to read a book that leaves readers reflecting on the nature of trust and the consequences of their actions.”*

- *I think Agatha Christie wrote this book to explore important themes such as political intrigues, personal sacrifice and the challenges of diplomacy in a world filled with conflicts. I took a lot of experience from this book and I am going to be a good diplomat like Stafford Nye. From this book I learnt about politics, human nature and the fight against oppression. I found “Passenger to Frankfurt” engaging and it blends mystery with a deeper message about the importance of standing up for justice. The morale questions raised in the book stayed with me long after we finish the book.”*

Students gained familiarity with the literary work's atmosphere during chapter discussions which functioned as both language practice exercises. Analyzing character motivation and plot twists allowed students to identify complex hero relationships which deepened their text comprehension and enhanced their ability to formulate arguments and share personal insights. Concerning the characters students wrote:

- *“I like the character of Mary Ann, because she is sharp, alert, kind and charismatic.”*

- *“If I could be someone in the “Passenger to Frankfurt”, I would choose Sir Stafford Nye. He has a unique character that leads him into exciting and dangerous situations.”*

- *“If it could be possible, I would be Lord (Edward) Altamont., who sacrificed himself for the government and state, also made a lot of political and risky missions during his life.”*

- *“I liked especially Lady Matilda. She has a clear vision about political issues and she is really knowledgeable. Reading her opinions towards any issues is a motivation to read this book further.”*

- *“My favorite character is Mary Ann who is the main character in this book. I just adore her because of her intelligence. Sometimes she showed herself to be so knowledgeable that I even wanted to be like her.”*

- *“If I could be someone in the story, I would like to be Sir Stafford Nye, of course. Because, he is like me – he can make strange but witty jokes.”*

In addition, it has helped to develop the ability to communicate across cultures. In the process of working with the book, students were exposed to cultural variabilities and differences, which was necessary for their future professional activity in the field of international relations. The book has become not only a tool for language practice but also a kind of cultural bridge, allowing students to understand more deeply the specifics of English literature and the perception of the world through the lens of Western culture.

Discussion of texts in a foreign language is a powerful tool for practicing live communication. In contrast to the passive perception of material, active participation in discussion helps students not only understand the text, but also develop skills of active listening, argumentation and public speaking.

During our classes, the students actively exchanged opinions about the characters and the story, which allowed them to use new words and expressions in context. Students engaged in small group discussions after completing each reading. In their discussions, students were expected to share their understandings of the text they had read as well as their comprehension strategy use. The discussions helped to overcome the language barrier, each student learned to make up their thoughts in a foreign language, even if they had to find equivalents and suitable expressions. As Knickerbocker & Rycik mentioned, discussions can provide students space to examine ideas and learn new ways of thinking and speaking (2006). It was a great way to improve your speaking skills and learn how to make more complex phrases.

Also, such discussions provide an opportunity to develop critical thinking. When students try to understand the actions of characters or deconstruct the motivation of heroes, they are forced not only to apply language constructs, but also to analyze, compare, draw conclusions. This is an important skill that will help them in any field of professional activity.

It is equally important that discussions in a foreign language promote self-confidence. When students discuss a book, they realize that their opinion is important and that they can effectively express their thoughts in a foreign language. This helps to build confidence in one’s own abilities and to use the language more freely in real situations.

As reading provides lots of opportunities developing basic foreign language skills on any global topic, while reading the book we dealt with many global issues like poverty, human rights, multiculturalism, environmental issues and their influence on us. This increased students’ engagement and they commented on text and talked about similarities and differences between our culture and those mentioned in the book, also they suggested some solutions to the challenges. Some students suggested even to make some changes in the book:

- *“If I had a chance I would make the ending of the story even better. For instance, I would focus on more about Aunt Matilda, about her work and her influence on politics.”*
- *“To make the book even better, I would add some characters from other nationalities as well. Because, as we know during World War there were many battles between other countries and I think it would be interesting to read about them too.”*

From the findings, it could be seen that reading books in teaching foreign languages provides a basis for entertaining and successful learning. In this process teachers perform a wide range of roles during their work with students in the classroom. To put it simply, the teacher equips the readers with not only knowledge of the language but also with skills, techniques and strategies which are essential for the reading process. (Let’s read in English). Here are some practical tips that can help make classes more productive and interesting:

- *Choosing a book based on the interests of students.* Teachers can provide the list of books with various options and students can choose from them according to their interest and the book which gained more votes can be the option for everyone. In our case, Agatha Christie was ideal for creating intriguing and entertaining discussions, as well as working with rich lexical and grammatical material.

- *Choosing the right level of book to read.* This will help students feel comfortable and confident.
- *Group discussions.* It is vital to create a collaborative atmosphere, let the students share their opinions, ask questions from each other, offer alternative interpretations. It develops communicative skills and helps students learn to listen and accept different points of view and express their thoughts and ideas freely.
- *Using different types of activities.* You can create role-playing games in which students play back scenes from a book or they can choose any part they like the most. This will help not only to learn the language, but also to develop creativity and students can explore their hidden talents as well. Also, in order to deepen the understanding of the book, you can use additional activities, such as interviews with authors, historical or cultural references about time and place. This widens horizons of the students and they may challenge themselves from different angles.

These methods can significantly increase students' interest in the learning process and help them not only in mastering the language, but also in developing analytical and cultural skills.

The discussions we had in class demonstrated how important it is not only to read, but also to actively interact with the text. This helps students better understand and absorb the material, as well as develop confidence in their language and communication skills.

Reading fictional books in teaching foreign languages opens up a lot of possibilities for teachers and students to be creative and to work deeply with texts. This experience can and should be continued by exploring more literature, broadening the horizons and deepening knowledge. In the end, literature becomes not only a tool for language learning, but also a key to deeper understanding of the world.

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